

Lifespan-prolonging Dual Battery System Online Operation Scheduling for In-city Drone Delivery

Yiliang Yuan^a, Jiahang Xie^b

^aDepartment of Industrial Systems Engineering and Management, National University of Singapore, Singapore 117576

^bSchool of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore 639798

[†] The two authors contribute equally to this work.

Abstract

Delivery conducted by drones is a significant role in in-city delivery and last-mile delivery cooperated with trucks, owing to their fast speed and economy. Despite all the remarkable advantages of the participation of drones in last-mile delivery, more challenges are introduced. Since drones are powered by batteries, battery lifetime and the associated replacement cost are one of the main hindrances to more cost-efficient drone applications in delivery. In this work, the lifetime-prolonging dual battery scheduling problem for drone operation is introduced. This problem is motivated by the real-world case where drones are utilized for healthcare delivery during the pandemic. As battery degradation induces the main cost in such application scenes, we propose a novel approach to make online decisions in the dual battery operation system to support drone flying tasks and reduce the cost of drone operation without future information concerning flying conditions. The dual battery consists of a new battery bank and a second-life battery bank, in which the scheduling can regulate the output of the new battery pack and thus extend its lifespan and meanwhile make full use of the abundant second-life battery resources. With the battery degradation model, the amortized operation cost curve including the battery reliability is derived. The online optimization algorithm is developed to solve the problem. Adopting the established dual battery schema, battery cost in the delivery system is reduced with new battery sustainable operation in the validation process.

Key words: Li-ion battery, Dual battery system, Online optimization, Battery lifespan extension, Drone delivery, Comparative ratio

1. Introduction

Deployment of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) has been prevalently outlined in logistics distribution [Murray & Chu \(2015\)](#). Drones are equipped with various sensors, and such advantages enable automated flight, object tracking, and collision avoidance. The solutions find the path with the shortest travel time among all possible options for a homogeneous fleet of vehicles each equipped with a single drone and able to serve several clients in a single trip. There is also a growing body of research on drone-related routing problems in supply chain management in recent years, as the drone-aided delivery paradigm offers more strengths than the truck-only delivery mode [Silva et al. \(2015\)](#).

The majority of drone delivery application is within last-mile delivery and in-city delivery. The battery pack is the primary energy source for drone operation, whose energy consumption is related to parcel payloads, flight ranges, and weather conditions. Concerning various applications in in-city delivery scenarios, for example, hospital health-care delivering drugs as a medical service during the pandemic, the weight of the package is not heavy and the flight duration is usually within one hour, thus within the drone's battery endurance time [Maheswari et al. \(2021\)](#). Besides, in the truck-drone delivery system, for instance, the batteries of drones can be recharged or replaced with fully-charged ones before they launch from trucks such that the capacity can support either a single visit to a customer node or multi-visits of drone service [Zhou et al.](#). Therefore, battery capacity restriction can be effectively resolved for in-city delivery.

Under the in-city delivery circumstance, the elimination of deteriorated batteries induces a large amount of cost in drone operation and maintenance [Shchurov et al. \(2021\)](#). Since in city flying conditions, drone flying tasks are comprised of frequent avoidance of densely populated infrastructures and confrontation against variable weather, the drone is required to change the posture to provide larger torque and strength, which is closely linked with battery discharge current and power [Bayrak et al. \(2020\)](#). Factors that help to fulfill flying missions, including power fluctuation and abrupt discharge stress, and short-term large current at the battery interface powering up the drone motion module, lead to fast battery degradation [Dörfler et al. \(2021\)](#). Besides, difficult weather conditions are going to put added pressure on the battery performance. Therefore, battery

1 lifetime and the associated replacement cost are one of the main hindrances to more cost-efficient
2 drone applications in delivery.

3 Li-ion takes a large percentage of drone battery energy sources. The battery lifespan is formally
4 defined as the period during which the battery can operate as intended and provides information
5 about the battery's long-term health. This important and useful measure, which indicates how long
6 the battery can function successfully, is inextricably linked to the decision-making process for
7 battery contingency mitigation, prognostics, and trouble identification [Xie et al. \(2022\)](#). When the
8 battery reaches the end of life, it will be eliminated for the sake of system safety and repurposed for
9 second-life usage.

10 With the purpose to reduce the drone maintenance cost induced by battery replacement, the
11 battery degradation process should be investigated such that approaches to extending battery lifetime
12 can be developed. Previous studies looked at the economics of extending battery longevity. The
13 objective function, which commonly comprises life loss cost, operating cost, and maintenance cost,
14 includes battery lifespan characteristics as battery cost [Zhao et al. \(2013\)](#). This tactic could work
15 well since the costs could discourage individuals from abusing the batteries. They are trying to find
16 a middle ground between two competing objectives: making the most of renewable energy sources
17 while maximizing battery life [Zhao et al. \(2013\)](#). However, the operating cost needs to be evaluated
18 carefully to prevent overly rough estimates based on the stated lifetime from the manufacturers
19 as well as to represent the deterioration process [Ercan et al. \(2015\)](#); [Hannan et al. \(2017\)](#). The
20 technical veracity of whether battery lifespan is extended is also lacking in the literature's current
21 studies; hence, the additional debate on the practicality of this sort of technique is necessary.

22 There are also technical approaches to extend battery service life. In [Xie et al. \(2022\)](#), the
23 relationships among battery operational conditions and expected lifespan are looked into. Thereafter,
24 control decisions are exerted on operation constraints to extend stationary battery energy storage
25 lifespan to the expected level. More importantly, as the drone may not always fly under appropriate
26 conditions, the flying posture in future times may not be accurately predictive by physical model.
27 Meanwhile, the drone discharge process may not follow certain protocols, e.g. constant current
28 (CC) or constant current - constant voltage (CCCV). Therefore, the battery operation in drone
29 requires instant operations and is thus suitable for online decision setup. Online optimization

1 deals with optimization problems having no or incomplete knowledge of the future. Whereas the
2 classical optimization problems with complete information is denoted as offline. Another reason for
3 employing the online optimization is the rather long time scale of battery degradation. In delivery
4 tasks, the time zones are comprised of a large amount of drone round trips, where each contains
5 several time intervals. Thus to optimize over the whole time horizon until the battery end of life
6 considering battery aging effect, relies on lots of decision variables in the overall time scale, thus
7 time consuming to solve.

8 The majority of the studies are limited to one battery set, thus more work is needed for the
9 scheduling between dual battery packs. To address the above issues, we propose the novel dual
10 battery operation scheduling paradigm for battery lifespan-prolonged in-city delivery for drones.
11 One new battery set works with the second-life battery set, thus the lifetime of the new battery set
12 can be prolonged since it is assigned to operate under smooth output conditions to generate savings
13 in terms of operation cost. Different flying tasks and postures of drones are associated with different
14 battery discharge currents and power [Zorbas & Douligeris \(2018\)](#), for instance, the drone hovering
15 state requires continuous and stable output from the battery set, whereas drone diving may require
16 transient and high power output [Abdulrahim & Lind \(2005\)](#). As stated above, more fluctuated
17 and higher power consumption will be covered by the cheaper and abundant second-life battery
18 resources. Besides, since the Li-ion battery is light in weight with high energy density, the weight
19 of two battery sets is acceptable for the in-city delivery drone type. To the best of our knowledge,
20 this is the first time the combination of the dual battery pair, one new and one serving second-life,
21 and the operation scheduling between two battery sets are considered to fulfill drone flying tasks
22 such that the overall operation cost with drone maintenance and protection cost is reduced based on
23 the extended lifetime of the new battery set.

24 A new sustainable and circular management of Li-ion assets is being promoted as the circular
25 economy has been invoked and elevated. In the energy storage industry, the circular economy would
26 like to encourage the usage of second-life batteries (SLB). SLBs are replaced by electrical vehicles,
27 smartphones, tablets, or drones, which have experienced around 20% capacity degradation, and
28 they have been utilized in stationary energy storage in the power grid [Waldmann et al. \(2017\)](#). Since
29 battery performance-oriented applications have been prevalent in the market for a long time, there

1 are plentiful SLBs available recently [Tao et al. \(2021\)](#). To make full use of the battery resource,
2 in this work, the SLBs are utilized as "old" battery sets to cooperate with the new battery set,
3 contributing to a more circular economic drone delivery operation.

4 Based on the newly proposed lifetime-prolonging dual battery scheduling problem, modeling
5 and solution techniques are further constructed to be applicable for practical scenarios. The
6 scheduling scheme constitutes the stepping stone for the dual battery management system. More
7 specifically, the aging effects of the new battery and SLB sets in terms of capacity degradation
8 speed difference given the same output performance is integrated into the model as the cost of
9 battery output following certain tasks of drones. Moreover, the reliability of battery sets is taken
10 into account. Reliability quantitatively describes the ability of a system or component to function
11 under stated conditions for a specified period [Henry & Ramirez-Marquez \(2012\)](#). Especially
12 for the SLB, there exists the risk of battery failure, thus collaboration with the new battery set
13 can keep the overall reliability on a high level. Whereas two second-life battery packs are more
14 likely to cause a security issue. Meanwhile, the reliability index of battery sets is involved to
15 form the offline optimization model accordingly. Furthermore, as the real-time scheduling of
16 two battery sets makes sequential decisions without future information and the battery discharge
17 process does not follow certain protocols [Wang et al. \(2017\)](#), the problem formulation follows
18 the online setting of mixed-integer programming (MIP) and is solved with an online optimization
19 algorithm to minimize the expectation of drone operation and battery maintenance cost under the
20 constraint that the drone power demand is assigned among the dual battery sets. The performance
21 of the adopted algorithm is verified on drone operation instances associated with the relationship
22 between battery output power and drone flying postures. The established online deterministic
23 scheduling algorithm shows good performance on generated test instances. For the evaluation of
24 battery life given the battery operational constraints corresponding to drone postures, we leverage
25 the newly developed battery lifetime estimation module in [Xie et al. \(2022\)](#) to provide technical
26 verification for the lifetime extension effect on the new battery set with the proposed drone battery
27 set scheduling mechanism. The main contributions of this paper are:Based on the newly proposed
28 lifetime-prolonging dual battery scheduling problem, modeling and solution techniques are further
29 constructed to be applicable for practical scenarios. The scheduling scheme constitutes the stepping

1 stone for the dual battery management system. More specifically, the aging effects of the new
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14 battery maintenance cost under the constraint that the drone power demand is assigned among the
15 dual battery sets. The performance of the adopted algorithm is verified on drone operation instances
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17 established online deterministic scheduling algorithm shows good performance on generated test
18 instances. For the evaluation of battery life given the battery operational constraints corresponding
19 to drone postures, we leverage the newly developed battery lifetime estimation module in [Xie et al.](#)
20 [\(2022\)](#) to provide technical verification for the lifetime extension effect on the new battery set with
21 the proposed drone battery set scheduling mechanism. The main contributions of this paper are:

- 22 1. Introduce the novel lifespan-prolonging dual battery scheduling functionality in battery
23 management systems for drone applications, where the coordination between new and SLB
24 sets is incorporated. And their different capacity degradation behaviors are considered to
25 quantify battery aging effects.
- 26 2. Construct an offline mixed-integer programming (MIP) model for the problem, consisting
27 of the operation cost curve amortized on capacity with consideration of reliability metrics
28 to prevent scheduling on failed battery. And convert the model with amortized cost to

1 facilitate online dispatch. Provide the theoretical proof for the comparative ratio of the
2 online deterministic scheduling algorithm solution to the dynamic programming scheduling
3 algorithm solution.

- 4 3. Duly applies an online algorithm to tackle the constructed problem without future data.
5 Evaluate the numerical results with a dynamic programming scheduling algorithm as a
6 benchmark to demonstrate the online output decision of battery packs. And examine the
7 lifetime extension effect for new battery sets within the optimal solution.

8 **2. Problem Statement**

9 *2.1. Influence of High Power Output on Battery*

10 Drone flying postures are significantly impacted by the surrounding environment like wind
11 speed and angle [Shepard et al. \(2016\)](#). For the drone to fly smoothly to accomplish delivery
12 assignments, the power supply system, i.e., the batteries, are required to produce varying output
13 and handle abrupt rather large or small power. As shown in the degradation model in [Jiang et al.](#)
14 [\(2019\)](#), the battery capacity decrease is closely linked to the output power. If continuously providing
15 high-level power, high charge and discharge throughput trigger an accelerated degradation process.
16 With the online scheduling system to handle abrupt power changes using two battery banks, the
17 new battery bank can have an extended lifespan under sustainable operation.

18 The reliability of batteries is another aspect influenced by unstable power output. Since high
19 power output induces a higher temperature rising in the Li-ion battery, a larger probability of failure
20 can be caused. Thus with the dual battery system, the failure rate of both battery banks is smaller
21 and the drone can effectively fulfill the delivery task. The designed dual battery system can make
22 full use of the abundant SLB resources and reduce costs in terms of operation and maintenance.

23 Studies regarding battery operation in the delivery problem settings are limited to the modeling
24 of energy consumption, also referred to as the endurance model. The estimates in [Stolaroff et al.](#)
25 [\(2018\)](#) show that the energy consumption rate depends on the payload and the travel distance. In
26 [Luo et al. \(2021\)](#) an endurance model based on both self-weight of the drone, payload, as well as
27 air time is adopted. Specifically, the authors consider energy consumption during the hovering time
28 when a drone is waiting for the truck to arrive in the truck-drone delivery system.

1 Furthermore, as summarized in [Macrina et al. \(2020\)](#), the limitation of battery operation is
2 converted into enforcing a maximum distance or a maximum flight time endurance for drones.
3 However such estimation of battery operation in flight can be rough, and oftentimes the pattern of a
4 drone's energy consumption is assumed to be linear for the sake of simplicity [Gonzalez-R et al.](#)
5 [\(2020\)](#). It is therefore important to closely investigate the battery power consumption mechanism
6 as well as the degradation effect to more accurately evaluate the cost of drone operation.

7 2.2. Dual Battery RUL-prolonging Scheduling System

8 Traditionally in EV production, dual battery systems have been developed to support different
9 levels of energy consumption and provide enough power. The vehicle's starter battery together with
10 the secondary battery is able to cover the power for driving and accessories.

11 In drone usage, similar advancements have also been witnessed. For example, DJI has designed
12 a drone that supports two batteries for longer flight time [Chen et al. \(2016\)](#). However, studies
13 regarding the power scheduling between dual battery banks in drones are limited. Particularly,
14 power dispatch between dual batteries for the sustainable extension of service life with the help of
15 second-life batteries is still not sufficiently understood.

16 Combining the fresh battery bank and the SLB, the dual battery power supply system is
17 demonstrated in [Fig. 1](#). The drone load is continuously supplied by either battery bank. And the
18 online dual battery management system is in charge of the scheduling task between two battery
19 banks, including smooth switch on/off of the associated converters, and the decision making
20 according to environment-oriented drone power load to extend the lifetime of the new battery pack.
21 Besides, the advantages and challenges of both types of batteries are listed for comparison. The
22 proposed dual battery lifespan-prolonging scheduling system architecture effectively leverages the
23 strengths and complements the weaknesses.

24 Following generally accepted definitions of battery lifetime, The end-of-life condition of the
25 new battery is $\frac{C_R}{C_I} \leq 80\%$, which denotes that the remaining capacity C_R is less than 80% of the
26 initial capacity C_I [Wu et al. \(2019\)](#). For the SLB, in drone application, it can be used until swelling
27 up or based on a customized standard to avoid potential hazards to the drone [Lorca et al. \(2020\)](#).
28 When the batteries are damaged, they must be replaced to ensure the drone safe operation.

Figure 1: Overview diagram of lifetime prolonging dual battery scheduling system

1 The necessity of online decision-making of the dual battery management system lies in the
 2 continuously and rapidly varying environmental conditions, whose changes may happen every few
 3 seconds. Thus it is time-consuming, inaccurate, and impractical to always predict the weather
 4 condition throughout the whole flight and perform optimization in advance. With the adopted
 5 online optimization algorithm, a constant competitive ratio can be achieved. The proof is detailed
 6 in section 4.3.

7 3. Mathematical Model for Lifespan-prolonging Dual Battery Scheduling of Drone Operation

8 3.1. Lithium-ion Battery Degradation Model and Simulation Pipeline

9 The capacity degradation of Li-ion batteries constitutes a large proportion of the drone mainte-
 10 nance cost, as the replacement of batteries leads to increasing investment at different stages. The
 11 component aging process of drones is not the focus of this work. In contrast, the deterioration of
 12 storage devices cannot be disregarded. Besides, the new battery bank and SLB bank have different
 13 degradation rates. Thus to extend the lifespan of the new battery bank and meanwhile minimize
 14 drone operation costs, the cost per unit time associated with the power output of the two battery

1 packs are different.

2 For the batteries, the capacity degradation can be differentiated as the superposition of the cycle
 3 degradation and the calendar degradation [Xu et al. \(2016\)](#). Battery cyclic and calendric lifespan
 4 indicators outline a battery usage pattern up to a certain capacity fading for a battery cell becomes
 5 apparent. The only wear-out factor taken into account in this investigation is riding. Self-discharge
 6 has a limited impact due to its low values, especially in lithium-ion battery chemistry.

For the lithium-ion battery type, the aging effect impact on the battery capacity is represented by
 the following equations [Omar et al. \(2014\)](#); [Tremblay & Dessaint \(2009\)](#). The capacity degradation
 depends on the rated energy capacity and the cycle number. The cumulative capacity deterioration
 of the battery pack over time interval n , given as a percentage, is the battery aging factor α .

$$\alpha_n = \begin{cases} \alpha_{n-1} + \frac{0.5}{L_{n-1}} \left(2 - \frac{DOD_{n-2} + DOD_n}{DOD_{n-1}} \right) & \text{if } k \bmod 2 \equiv 1 \\ \alpha_{n-1} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

7 with $n = kT_h, k \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, where the notations have the meanings as follows. T_h is the half-cycle
 8 duration in seconds. A complete cycle is obtained when the battery goes through a full charge and
 9 discharge procedure. DOD is the battery depth of discharge $DOD = 1 - SOC(\%)$ after a half-cycle
 10 duration. L is the maximum number of cycles and is given by:

$$L_n = H \left(\frac{DOD_n}{100} \right)^{-\xi} \cdot \exp\left(-\psi \left(\frac{1}{T_{ref}} - \frac{1}{T_n^a} \right)\right) \cdot (I_{dis_ave})^{-\gamma_1} \cdot (I_{ch_ave})^{-\gamma_2} \quad (2)$$

11 H is the equivalent cycle number of a battery in which the battery capacity reduces from the
 12 beginning of use to the end of its life [Abdollahi et al. \(2017\)](#). ξ is the exponent factor for the depth
 13 of discharge. ψ is the Arrhenius rate constant for the cycle number [Zheng et al. \(2019\)](#). I_{dis_ave}
 14 is the average discharge current in A during a half cycle duration and correspondingly I_{ch_ave} is
 15 the average charge current in A during a half cycle duration. γ_1, γ_2 are the exponent factor for the
 16 discharge current and charge current respectively.

Thus, the useable energy capacity evolution of the battery after the time interval n can be written

as:

$$\hat{Q}_n = \begin{cases} Q^r - \alpha_n \cdot (Q^r - Q_{EOL}) & \text{if } k \bmod 2 \equiv 1 \\ \hat{Q}_{n-1} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

1 Q^r is the battery's rated capacity in Ah, at the beginning of life and nominal ambient temperature.
 2 Q_{EOL} is the battery's capacity in Ah, at the end of life and nominal ambient temperature. The aging
 3 factor α is equal to zero and unity at the beginning of life and end of life.

4 The constraint for the useable energy capacity of the battery after the time interval n can be
 5 expressed as:

$$SOH_{end} \cdot Q^r \leq \hat{Q}_n \leq SOH_{initial} \cdot Q^r \quad (4)$$

6 The battery's remaining capacity can be compared to the nominal capacity and the ratio is defined
 7 as the state of health (SOH) [Xiong et al. \(2018\)](#). When the battery's SOH reaches SOH_{end} ,
 8 which denotes the end of its life, it is presumed that the battery has been discarded. Additionally,
 9 $SOH_{initial}$ represents the SOH at the start of use. From the above equations, the aging model is
 10 approximated as the relationship with the charging/discharging cycle, state of charge (SOC), and
 11 charging/discharging current.

Moreover, we look into the degradation rate of the battery based on model (3). The change of
 battery capacity $Q(n)$ at each iteration step is:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{Q}_n - \hat{Q}_{n-1} &= (Q^r - Q_{EOL})(\alpha_{n-1} - \alpha_n) \\ &= (Q^r - Q_{EOL}) \cdot \frac{0.5}{L_{n-1}} \left(\frac{DOD_{n-2} + DOD_n}{DOD_{n-1}} - 2 \right), \quad n = kT_h, k \bmod 2 \equiv 1 \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

12 in which under the constant current (CC) operation condition with fixed C-rates in each time
 13 step, L_{n-1} is a constant as well. Thus the capacity degradation rate within the model under
 14 CC charging/discharging mode is a constant value under specified C-rates and environmental
 15 temperature T^a . In [Zhang et al. \(2018\)](#) the capacity degradation curve is deemed as a linear
 16 relationship with time as well as the battery degradation process is rather long. And the degradation
 17 rate as the slope, is a constant value under each operation condition.

1 The degradation rates still vary among the new battery bank and the SLB under the same opera-
 2 tion condition. Based on the above battery degradation model, the battery operation simulations
 3 can be conducted in Simulink/MATLAB to monitor the capacity deterioration trajectory and derive
 4 the degradation rate of batteries under different power output, which can be utilized to calculate the
 5 operation cost of new battery and SLB. The cost is integrated into the offline optimization model to
 6 help extend the service lifespan of new battery packs.

7 Referring to the data-driven approach proposed in Xie et al. (2022), the simulation of both new
 8 and old batteries can be conducted under various operating conditions with different output power
 9 related to charging/discharging current. The flow chart for the simulation is demonstrated in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Flow chart of simulation to derive battery degradation rate under different output power conditions

10 The battery operates in constant current (CC) mode because, in online optimization, the
 11 environment may be assumed to remain static for each brief time step Δt . Additionally, the drone's
 12 load may be thought of as a constant value, denoting a constant current value. It is also feasible to
 13 support different modes. The basic steps of the simulation technique are as follows.

- 14 1. Set the sampling number of operating conditions.

- 1 2. Give the simulation model's input operating conditions, such as the SOC range [$\underline{\text{SOC}}, \overline{\text{SOC}}$]
2 and charge/discharge current [$\mathbf{I}_c, \mathbf{I}_d$].
- 3 3. Cycles of charging and discharging are ongoing. The battery approaches the end of its useful
4 life when the remaining capacity, C_R is less than 80% of the original capacity C_I . This is
5 referred to as the termination condition for new batteries, which is $\frac{C_R}{C_I} \leq 80\%$. Based on a
6 specified level, the end-of-life condition for SLB can be $\frac{C_R}{C_I} \leq 50\%$.
- 7 4. Obtain the capacity process data and determine the degradation rate appropriately if the
8 termination condition is satisfied. End the simulation if the chosen sample number of
9 simulations has been completed. If not, repeat steps 2-3.

10 Based on the simulation rule, the data set of battery degradation rates under different power
11 output can be obtained. It is important to note that actual data on aging and lifespan projections are
12 extremely susceptible to a variety of influencing factors, including test settings, cell construction
13 type, sealing quality, and electrolyte additions [Bukhari et al. \(2015\)](#). Additionally, the values may
14 differ amongst batteries made by different manufacturers. The accuracy of the available lifespan
15 data is not the main concern of this investigation, though. The patterns are in line with the body
16 of research, and lifetime estimates generated in this work are in line with the makers of battery's
17 extensive experience.

18 3.2. Dual Battery System Reliability

19 The likelihood that a product will perform properly for the stipulated time frame when utilized
20 following the prescribed circumstances is known as reliability. The frequency with which a designed
21 system or component fails, on the other hand, is known as the failure rate. The dual new and
22 second-life battery packs can be deemed as a parallel power supply system for reliability assessment,
23 in which the two banks have independent performance owing to the switch circuit between them
24 for isolation [Xing et al. \(2011\)](#). Thus the drone load cannot be supported if both battery banks have
25 the fault.

26 The dual battery system reliability is closely linked to the drone power demand as well as
27 the investment on battery replacement upon failure, thus needs to be included in the optimization

1 model. Under the load supply application scenario, the following reliability indices can be utilized
 2 to evaluate the battery performance and adequacy of the system.

3 Regarding drone performance, the reliability index Expected Energy Not Served (EENS) can be
 4 used as the metric to evaluate the cost caused by battery failure and measure the security of supply
 5 [Teixeira & Borges \(2020\)](#); [Liu et al. \(2017\)](#), which is related to the electricity required for user and
 6 system grid structure. For a state k that experiences load shedding as a result of inadequate power
 7 availability or dual battery asset failures, λ_k is the likelihood of it happening; L_k is the amount of
 8 load shedding; t_k is the average fault duration for such a state k , and S is the total number of states
 9 experiencing load shedding. The indices are updated according to:

$$EENS = \sum_{k=1}^S \lambda_k L_k t_k \quad (6)$$

10 Other indices such as the loss of load probability (LOLP) can be considered as well [Jurasz](#)
 11 [et al. \(2020\)](#). Its values can range from 0% to 100%, where values closer to zero denote a lower
 12 probability of failure in covering the energy demand.

$$LOLP = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N E_t^{DNC}}{\sum_{t=1}^N E_t^D} \times 100\% \quad (7)$$

13 where E_t^{DNC} denotes energy demand not covered (kWh) in time step t and E_t^D denotes energy
 14 demand (kWh). Thus LOLP can be deemed as the probability of failure. Following the definition
 15 of LOLP, the battery reliability curve at different drone load demand levels is depicted in Fig. 3.

16 The cumulative failure distribution of the battery about load level can be generally written
 17 as $F(p^D) = 1 - e^{-((p^D - \gamma)/a)^b}$, including the charge, discharge, and standby times of the battery
 18 module [Liu et al. \(2016\)](#). It indicates the fraction of the population failing at load level p^D . And
 19 correspondingly, the reliability or survivor function $R(p^D) = 1 - F(p^D)$ indicates the probability of
 20 survival. Parameters a, b, γ can be extracted from the statistical distribution and vary between the
 21 new battery and SLB.

Figure 3: Battery failure function and reliability function

3.3. Offline Model Formulation and Operation Cost Curves on Amortized Capacity Degradation

For the drone delivery flying task optimization, the dispatch configuration for the dual battery system is computed by solving the following offline mathematical formulation:

$$\min_{\mathcal{B}_v} \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \left\{ [(\hat{E}C_{i,T}^s - E_{i,T}^s)\pi_E + \omega^s(\hat{Q}_{i-1,T}^s - \hat{Q}_{i,T}^s)] + \sum_{t=1}^T [|x_{i,t}^s - x_{i,t-1}^s|\pi_s + \mathbb{P}^s(p_{i,t}^{s,d})\pi_B] \right\} \quad (8a)$$

Power load balance:

$$0 \leq p_{i,t}^{s,d} \leq x_{i,t}^s \bar{p}_{i,t}^s, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, i \in N, t \in T \quad (8b)$$

$$p_{i,t}^{N,d} + p_{i,t}^{O,d} = p_{i,t}^D, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, i \in N, t \in T \quad (8c)$$

$$x_{i,t}^N + x_{i,t}^O \leq 1, \quad x_{i,t}^s \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, i \in N, t \in T \quad (8d)$$

Battery state:

$$E_{i,t}^s = E_{i,t-1}^s + p_{i,t}^{s,c} \Delta t \eta^{s,c} - p_{i,t}^{s,d} \Delta t / \eta^{s,d}, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, i \in N, t \in T \quad (8e)$$

$$\underline{E}_{i,t}^s \leq E_{i,t}^s \leq EC_{i,t}^s, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, i \in N, t \in T \quad (8f)$$

$$\hat{E}C_{i,t}^s = \hat{Q}_{i,t}^s V_B^r, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, i \in N, t \in T \quad (8g)$$

Battery degradation model:

$$(1) - (4)$$

1 In the objective function, the total cost for drone operation with a dual battery power supply system
 2 is minimized. The summation consists of the charging cost for each flight mission after the drone
 3 returns to the depot, the capacity degradation, the switching cost between two battery banks, and
 4 the expectation of battery replacement cost considering the reliability index. The capacity loss cost
 5 and battery elimination cost can be counted as maintenance costs.

6 More precisely in (8a), N is the number of delivery tasks, and T is the total time steps in each
 7 flight. \mathcal{S} denotes the battery pack in use, either the new battery or the SLB bank. \mathcal{B}_v represents
 8 the set of decision variables, i.e., $\mathcal{B}_v = \{\hat{E}C_{i,t}^s, E_{i,t}^s, \hat{Q}_{i,t}^s, x_{i,t}^s, p_{i,t}^{s,d}\}$, meaning the battery current energy
 9 capacity, energy, capacity, switch state or the battery pack in use (state N stands for new battery
 10 pack and state O stands for SLB), output power, respectively. Therefore, the first term indicates
 11 battery charging cost due to consumed energy compared to the current round energy capacity, with
 12 π_E as the electricity price. Similarly, the second term denotes the cost associated with capacity
 13 degradation, with ω^s as the penalty weight. The two terms are meaningful after a comparatively
 14 longer period and thus are calculated after each flight. The last two terms are the instant cost within
 15 each time step of the flight. π_s is the operating cost coefficient for the battery switch, in which the
 16 consecutive two time steps are considered. \mathbb{P}^s is the failure rate function relevant to power output
 17 $p_{i,t}^{s,d}$ derived from section 3.2 and π_B^s is the corresponding capital cost for battery bank.

18 For constraints that constitute the feasible region, three aspects: the drone power load balance,
 19 the battery status, and the battery degradation characteristics are involved. In the power load balance
 20 constraints, (8b) regulates the output power of both battery packs through the binary variable $x_{i,t}^s$.
 21 (8c) satisfies the drone's power demand. The outsourced electricity of the dual battery system is the
 22 electricity required by the load side. And the dual battery system each time step with one battery
 23 pack to provide the electricity can be expressed as (8d). States of the two battery banks at any time
 24 interval can not be both in discharging state simultaneously.

25 In battery state constraints, (8e) describes the battery's remaining energy after charging/discharging
 26 in the current time step. Δt is the elapsed time during the time interval t . As the drone power demand
 27 varies with the second magnitude, Δt is also taken as $1s$. $\eta^{s,c}, \eta^{s,d}$ are the charging/discharging
 28 efficiency. Since $\frac{E_{i,t}^s}{\hat{E}C_{i,t}^s}$ denotes the battery SOC, the battery SOC restriction can be written as (8f).
 29 The maximum and minimum SOC of the battery can be customized. (8g) is determined by the

1 relationship between the battery current energy capacity and the capacity, given nominal voltage V_B^r
 2 for a certain type of battery.

3 The integration of the battery degradation model completes the physics-aware offline optimiza-
 4 tion model. From the battery's initial health state, the capacity deteriorates in the drone operation
 5 process. In the following part, we equivalently simplify the offline optimization model by amortiz-
 6 ing operation cost into a unit of time to facilitate the development of solution algorithms in section
 7 4.2.

8 Since within the battery operating condition setting in this work, the degradation rates are
 9 constant at each output power level as in (5), the replacement cost of end-of-life batteries in the
 10 objective function can be amortized to the unit of capacity. That is to say, the terms of battery
 11 capacity loss cost and the expectation of failure re-investment cost in the objective function (8a)
 12 are decoupled and transferred as the cost for battery output energy amount. The corresponding
 13 cost function is $c_{i,t}^s(p_{i,t}^{s,d})$, indicating the cost value related to the battery discharge power. And the
 14 objective function becomes:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \left\{ (\hat{E}C_{i,T}^s - E_{i,T}^s) \pi_E + \sum_{t=1}^T [|x_{i,t}^s - x_{i,t-1}^s | \pi_s + c_{i,t}^s(p_{i,t}^{s,d})] \right\} \quad (9)$$

15 More precisely, the maintenance investment measured in dollar (\$) is amortized on the usable
 16 capacity first, i.e., as the cost for unit capacity (\$/Ah). Then as the capacity loss is measured in
 17 Ah/s, the multiplication of the two quantities produces the unit time operation cost measured in \$/s
 18 under specific power output values. Therefore, as the model time step Δt is also for each second,
 19 the power supply cost in each time step of both the new battery and SLB can be obtained.

20 To transfer the probabilistic-based optimization model into a solvable formulation, battery
 21 risk potential represented by the reliability function is also incorporated into the operation cost
 22 amortized on capacity. The failure rates are associated with battery replacement and therefore act
 23 as a larger coefficient for the capacity amortized cost.

24 In this way, the offline objective function can be equivalently converted to the objective function
 25 accounting for operation cost based on battery power output. And such cost is comprised of capacity
 26 degradation due to usage and the replacement because of end of service lifespan or failure. Such

1 “penalties” are directly related to the power output and differ between the new battery and SLB, thus
2 batteries’ output will be effectively limited. The linearity within the capacity degradation model
3 facilitates the design of both offline and online optimization algorithms.

4 **4. Optimization Algorithms**

5 In this section, constructive procedures of the employed algorithms are demonstrated for
6 solving the lifetime-prolonging dual battery scheduling problem. Firstly, we discuss the dynamic
7 programming scheduling algorithm to solve the offline problem to provide the optimal solution as
8 the benchmark. Secondly, we propose online optimization algorithms, including the probabilistic
9 scheduling algorithm and the deterministic scheduling algorithm for comparison purposes. Last
10 but not the least, proof for the objective value bound of the deterministic scheduling algorithm is
11 provided as well.

12 *4.1. Dynamic Programming Offline Optimization Algorithm*

13 Since the operation and maintenance cost of both new battery and SLB packs have been
14 amortized into unit time, the optimization model in section 3.3 can be solved with the dynamic
15 programming (DP) algorithm. And the cost is additive owing to the linearity of capacity loss rate
16 at each power output level under the battery operation condition setting. So the cost for N drone
17 flights is the summation of each cost value. In the offline mode, the drone operation output power
18 during the whole flying timespan in different tasks is known, e.g., based on the prediction learned
19 from historical data, thus the dynamic programming scheduling algorithm can give the optimal
20 solution of battery operation scheduling.

21 **Algorithm 1** The offline dynamic programming scheduling algorithm

22 **Input:** Drone flight data, battery capacity amortized operation cost, switch cost

23 **Output:** Minimized operation cost and battery switch sequence

24 **if** $t = T$ (boundary conditions satisfied) **then**

25 return 0

26 **end if**

27 **if** $s = 0$ (new battery in use) **then**

```

1     return min( $c_{i,t}^N \Delta t + f(0, t + 1)$ ,  $c_{i,t}^O \Delta t + \pi_s + f(1, t + 1)$ )
2 else
3     return min( $c_{i,t}^O \Delta t + \pi_s + f(0, t + 1)$ ,  $c_{i,t}^N \Delta t + f(1, t + 1)$ )
4 end if

```

5 In the top-down dynamic programming algorithm 1 with known future information, the state
6 includes the battery in operation s and the current time step t . In the status, 0 denotes the new
7 battery is in use in the current time step, while 1 denotes the SLB is in use. With the amortized
8 operation cost in each time step computed with the output power value as c_t^N, c_t^O , the Bellman
9 equation is expressed for the dynamic programming. The objective minimization is solely related
10 to the current time step and irrelevant to past states. The problem is then solved recursively by
11 breaking the problem into sub-problems with optimal substructure and the solution is treated as the
12 benchmark for comparison with online optimization results.

13 4.2. Online Optimization Algorithm

14 DP results are the benchmark as it owns the information in the whole timespan, whereas online
15 algorithms have the information in the current time step and historical data. In online optimization
16 without future information, the probabilistic-based intuitive algorithm is shown as Algorithm 2.

17 **Algorithm 2** The online probabilistic scheduling algorithm

18 **Input:** Drone flight data in the current time slot, battery capacity amortized operation cost,
19 switch cost

20 **Output:** Minimized operation cost and battery switch sequence

21 $N_{cnt} \leftarrow 0, O_{cnt} \leftarrow 0$

22 **for** $0 \leq t \leq T$ **do**

23 $c_{i,t}^N = \mathcal{D}^N(p^d), c_{i,t}^O = \mathcal{D}^O(p^d), rnd \leftarrow random()$

24 **if** $N_{cnt} \geq O_{cnt}$ **then**

25 **if** $rnd \geq N_{cnt}/(N_{cnt} + O_{cnt} + 1)$ **then**

26 SLB in use, $N_{cnt} \leftarrow 0, O_{cnt} \leftarrow 1$

27 **else**

28 New battery in use, $N_{cnt} \leftarrow N_{cnt} + 1$

```

1     end if
2     else
3         Switch similarly
4     end if
5 end for

```

6 The switch criterion between the new battery SLB pack is the frequency of occurrence since the
7 last switch. More specifically, a random number is sampled from the uniform distribution within
8 $[0, 1]$. If the picked random number is larger than the frequency, the battery in use will be switched.
9 The frequency of occurrence can be interpreted as the trend of adopting which battery since the
10 last switch. And it reflects within the recent period, whether the surrounding environment requires
11 increased power output. If so, the switch status tends to remain the same. The drawback of this
12 algorithm is that it cannot react appropriately when the time-dependent power output is not stable.

13 The deterministic scheduling algorithm is shown as Algorithm 3. The switch criterion here is
14 the accumulated cost comparison between the new battery and SLB pack since the last switch. In
15 this way, the switch happens hysteretically, yet the switch action will not be easily affected by the
16 fluctuation in power output.

17 **Algorithm 3** The online deterministic scheduling algorithm

18 **Input:** Drone flight data in the current time slot, battery capacity amortized operation cost,
19 switch cost

20 **Output:** Minimized operation cost and battery switch sequence

21 $N_c \leftarrow 0, O_c \leftarrow 0$

22 **for** $0 \leq t \leq T$ **do**

23 $c_{i,t}^N = \mathcal{D}^N(p^d), c_{i,t}^O = \mathcal{D}^O(p^d), N_c \leftarrow N_c + c_{i,t}^N, O_c \leftarrow O_c + c_{i,t}^O$

24 **if** *previous switch state* = 0 **then**

25 **if** $O_c + \pi_s \leq N_c$ **then**

26 SLB in use, $N_c \leftarrow c_{i,t}^N, O_c \leftarrow c_{i,t}^O$

27 **else**

28 New battery in use

```

1     end if
2     else
3         Switch similarly
4     end if
5 end for

```

6 The time complexity of the dynamic programming algorithm is $O(N \cdot s \cdot T)$, in which N means
7 the number of total flights, s denotes the status of the battery in use, either the new battery or the
8 SLB bank, and T is the total time steps for each flight. It is worth mentioning that in the online
9 deterministic optimization algorithm, in each time step, the algorithm can effectively tackle the
10 problem with $O(1)$ time complexity.

11 With the proposed algorithm, the objective value is guaranteed to be within four times compared
12 to the dynamic programming results. The proof is given in the following section.

13 4.3. Competitive Ratio Analysis of Online Algorithm

14 To analyze the competitive ratio of the proposed online deterministic scheduling algorithm, we
15 compare the offline optimal solution OPT and the solution from the online algorithm OL . The
16 costs of the optimal solution and online solution are denoted as C_{OPT} and C_{OL} . Furthermore, we
17 use $OPT(t)$ and $OL(t)$ to represent the battery status at time slot t under optimal solution and online
18 algorithm solution. For example, $OPT(t) = 0$ if the battery in use at time slot t under optimal
19 solution is new battery, otherwise the battery in use is second life battery.

20 First, we discuss the definition of competitive ratio. The competitive ratio is defined as the
21 ratio between the cost of the online algorithm and the optimal cost, which is always larger than 1.
22 A better online algorithm will have a competitive ratio more close to 1. The simple definition of
23 competitive ratio $\frac{C_{OPT}}{C_{OL}}$ is not suitable in our setting. Note that for each task, there is a fixed cost
24 independent of the battery status $\min\{c_t^O, c_t^N\}$, which means no matter what the scheduling algorithm
25 is, there is always a fixed cost. To better evaluate our online algorithm, we use $\eta = \frac{C_{OL} - \sum_{t=0}^T \min\{c_t^O, c_t^N\}}{C_{OPT} - \sum_{t=0}^T \min\{c_t^O, c_t^N\}}$
26 as the competitive ratio. It is easy to prove that this ratio is larger than $\frac{C_{OPT}}{C_{OL}}$.

27 The time horizon are divided into several segments such that the optimal solution, the battery in
28 each segment is the same and the status switch only happens at the first time slot in each segment.

1 Consider a segment $[i, j]$, where the switch in optimal solution happens at time i . In this segment,
2 the online algorithm switches several times: online switch from 0 to 1 for α times and from 1 to 0
3 for β times. If there is a competitive ratio for each segment, when we sum up costs in all segments,
4 this competitive ratio also holds. Thus, for the sake of simplicity, we focus on a segment $[\mu, v]$
5 such that battery status at each time under optimal solution is always 0. For the segment where the
6 optimal solution is always 1, the same result still holds.

7 To better illustrate the competitive ratio, the following notations are introduced.

- 8 • $c_0(t) = c_t^O - c_t^N$, if $c_t^O \geq c_t^N$, otherwise 0.
- 9 • $c_1(t) = c_t^N - c_t^O$, if $c_t^N \geq c_t^O$, otherwise 0.
- 10 • $f_0(t) = c_0(t)$ if $OL(t) = 1$ and $c_t^O \geq c_t^N$, otherwise 0.
- 11 • $f_1(t) = c_1(t)$ if $OL(t) = 0$ and $c_t^N \geq c_t^O$, otherwise 0.

12 The cost of the online algorithm in this segment consists of two parts: battery cost and switch
13 cost. In the following computation, we assign each switch cost to several time slots. If the online
14 algorithm switch to 0 at time a and switch to 1 at time b , the cost of the switch to 1 is assigned to
15 each slot in this time $[a, b]$. A unit cost is $\frac{\pi_s}{\sum_{l=a}^b c_{l,1}}$, and for each time slot l , the assigned switch cost
16 is $\frac{\pi_s}{\sum_{l=a}^b c_{l,1}} c_l(1)$. The total assigned cost in $[a, b]$ is π_s .

17 **Proposition 1.** $C_{OPT} \geq \pi_s + \sum_{l \in [\mu, v]} c_1(l)$

18 *Proof.* Note that in this segment, battery status in optimal solution is always 0, which means the
19 task l will occur in a battery cost only if $c_l^N < c_l^O$. Thus the total battery cost is $\sum_{l \in [\mu, v]} c_1(l)$. The
20 switch for an optimal solution only happens at the first time slot, which means the switching cost in
21 this segment is π_s . □

22 **Proposition 2.** $C_{OPT} \geq \sum_{l \in [\mu, v]} f_0(l) - 2\beta\pi_s + \pi_s$

Proof. For each frame $[a_i, b_i]$ in this segment where the $OL(l) = 1, \forall l \in [a_i, b_i]$, since the online
algorithm does not switch at time b_i , we have $\sum_{l \in [a_i, b_i]} c_0(l) + 2\pi_s \leq \sum_{l \in [a_i, b_i]} c_1(l)$. Thus, we have

the following bound for C_{OPT} .

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{OPT} &= \sum_{l \in [\mu, v]} c_1(l) + \pi_s \\
&\geq \pi_s + \sum_i \left(\sum_{l \in [a_i, b_i]} C_0(l) - 2\pi_s \right) \\
&\geq \sum_{l \in [\mu, v]}^v f_0(l) - 2\beta\pi_s + \pi_s
\end{aligned}$$

1 □

2 **Proposition 3.** $C_{OPT} > 2\alpha\pi_s + \pi_s$

Proof. Consider each time the online algorithm switch from 0 to 1, we have $\sum_c 1(0) \geq \sum c_0 + 2\pi_s \geq 2\pi_s$. Thus, we have the following lower bound for the optimal solution.

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{OPT} &\geq \alpha * (2\pi_s) + \pi_s \\
&\geq 2\beta\pi_s - \pi_s
\end{aligned}$$

3 The second inequality is because $\alpha \geq \beta - 1$, which means each time the online algorithm switches
4 from 0 to 1, it must switch from 1 to 0 before. □

5 In terms of cost of online algorithm, it consists of four parts:

- 6 • Cost of switching from 1 to 0, which is upper bounded by $\alpha\pi_s$;
- 7 • Cost of switching from 0 to 1. Recall we introduced above the unit cost, we know each unit
8 cost is at most $1/2$. Thus, the total cost is upper bounded by $0.5 \sum_{l \in [\mu, v]} c_1(l)$;
- 9 • Battery cost when new battery is in use, which is upper bounded by $\sum_{l \in [\mu, v]} c_1(l)$;
- 10 • Battery cost when second life battery is in use, which is $\sum_{l \in [\mu, v]} f_0(l)$.

11 Now we are ready to provide a performance guarantee for the online algorithm.

12 **Theorem 1.** *The competitive ratio for the online algorithm is at most 4.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{OL} &\leq \beta\pi_s + \sum_{l \in [\mu, v]} f_0(l) + 1.5 \sum_{l \in [\mu, v]} c_1(l) + \pi_s \\
&\leq 1.5 \left(\sum_{l \in [\mu, v]} C_1(l) + 1.5\pi_s \right) + 1.5(2\beta\pi_s - \pi_s) + \left(\sum_{l \in [\mu, v]} f_0(l) - 2\beta\pi_s + \pi_s \right) \\
&\leq 4C_{OPT}
\end{aligned}$$

1 Thus, the competitive ratio $\frac{C_{OL}}{C_{OPT}}$ is smaller than 4. □

2 **5. Computational Experiments**

3 In this section, the numerical results concerning the battery degradation rate amortized operation
4 cost for new battery and SLB, and optimization results of the lifespan-prolonging dual battery
5 power supply scheduling for a series of drone flights are displayed. Furthermore, the performance
6 of algorithms is analyzed. The validation based on the battery model in Simulink/MATLAB
7 demonstrates the lifetime extension effect of the proposed dual battery system compared to drone
8 operation with only one new battery pack. The algorithms are implemented in Python3.8, running
9 on a desktop PC with a 1.80 GHz Intel(R) Xeon(R) Silver 4108 processor and 32GB of memory.

10 *5.1. Drone Flight and Li-ion Battery Test Instances*

11 The drone flight dataset is adopted from instances generated in [Rodrigues et al. \(2020\)](#). The
12 information of each flight was simultaneously collected during flight campaigns from onboard
13 sensors. Experimental data include wind speed, drone battery current, voltage, as well as drone
14 flying speed acceleration, and location. The DJI Matrice 100 quadrotor platform is utilized. The
15 drone has a maximum flight speed of 17 m/s and a maximum takeoff weight of 3.6 kg.

16 During the flight duration, the drone launches first, during which period the output power
17 gradually increases. Then within the flying interval, the output power is correlated with wind speed
18 and angle. The output power fluctuates and can have sudden oscillation. At the end of the flight,
19 the drone lands with decreasing power output.

In the simulation setup, the time interval Δt is set as 1s because drone power demand is time-varying with the peripheral environment. It is also ensured that in each flight the drone battery SOC level will not exceed the lower limit as constrained in (8f).

The drone’s standard battery has a capacity of 4500 mAh. Thus the battery simulation setup follows the same nominal capacity, using $LiCoO_2$ cell. The drone also can choose to install the optional battery with 5700 mAh as another type of Lithium polymer battery. In the simulation, another $LiFePO_4$ battery with a different numerical degradation rate is tested as well. In the following simulation results, the standard 4500 mAh battery is denoted as “Bat 1” and the optional 5700 mAh battery is denoted as “Bat 2”.

Specifications of the two kinds of battery modules are described in Table 1. The delivery flight simulations are tested on the two kinds of batteries, each formulating the dual battery system with one new pack and one SLB pack.

Table 1: Li-ion batteries specification

Parameter	Bat 1 ($LiCoO_2$)	Bat 2 ($LiFePO_4$)
Nominal Capacity	4.5Ah	5.7Ah
Nominal voltage	22.2V	22.8V
Energy	99.9Wh	129.96Wh
Net weight	600g	676g
Max. charging power	180W	180W
Operating temperature	$-10^{\circ}C - 40^{\circ}C$	$-10^{\circ}C - 40^{\circ}C$
Charging temperature	$0^{\circ}C - 40^{\circ}C$	$0^{\circ}C - 40^{\circ}C$

5.2. Battery Degradation Rate and Amortized Operation Cost

For the battery operation in drones, without loss of generality, the main concern lies in the discharge process with time-varying peripheral conditions and the current can reach high C-rate levels. Whereas the charging process is performed at the depot and the charging process is assumed under rated working conditions of the battery. Therefore, for the charging operation, current I_c is set as 1C. In contrast, the discharging current I_d ranges from 1C to 8C according to the drone operation dataset. Based on the consideration of drone endurance and operation safety, both Li-ion battery packs are kept within the state of charge (SOC) range 10% – 100% such that the batteries

1 are not drained.

2 For the new battery bank, the end-of-life SOH is 80%, matching a typical replacement criterion
 3 for drone application. And the SLB end-of-life SOH is chosen as 50% [Montoya-Bedoya et al. \(2020\)](#).
 4 The ambient temperature is assumed to be constant at 25°C. The corresponding capacity variation
 5 slope is obtained based on the simulation procedure in section 3.1. The curves of degradation rates
 6 are regressed with different power outputs, such that for online applications, the drone’s required
 7 power can link to the degradation of the battery to provide the load demand.

8 The following visualization show detailed experimental result. The battery capacity degradation
 9 rates under different power outputs and the amortized cost curve are illustrated in Fig. 4 based on
 10 the selected power samples. The cost prices for the new battery and SLB pack are 199\$ and 45\$
 11 respectively [Kamath et al. \(2020\)](#). For the second type of battery “Bat 2”, the simulation results are
 12 similar.

Figure 4: Capacity amortized battery operation cost curve based on degradation rate under different drone power demand

13 The SLB degradation rate is higher than that of the new battery pack. But since in the amortized
 14 cost $c_{i,t}^s(p_{i,t}^{s,d})$, the replacement cost together with the failure rates in Fig. 4(a) are multiplied as the
 15 coefficients to degradation rate, the cost curves of two battery banks have the intersection point
 16 as in Fig. 4(b). The meaning is that at the low power output level, using the new battery bank
 17 is more cost-efficient, because the capacity loss in the new battery is small and the reliability is
 18 high at this power level such that the lifetime of the new battery can be extended with reduced

1 re-investment cost. Whereas under the large power output, using the SLB is more cost-efficient,
 2 though the capacity loss and average failure rate are comparatively higher than that of the new
 3 battery, the re-investment price of SLB is lower, and thus the amortized cost is lower with the
 4 adjustment effect of coefficients.

5 The comparison between the amortized curve and the distribution of drone power within all
 6 flights is depicted in Fig. 5.

Figure 5: Comparison between the amortized curve and the distribution of drone power

7 The drone power during the taking off and landing phases are on a low level, thus in the
 8 distribution, there is a substantial number of time steps with a small power value. In the flying
 9 phase, the power distribution is similar to the Weibull distribution, which is widely used to represent
 10 the distribution of wind speed [Akgül et al. \(2016\)](#). The intersection point of the amortized cost
 11 curves can correspond to the drone power with high occurrence frequency. Thus the dual battery
 12 system switch phase is meant to help minimize the operation cost of drones.

13 5.3. Lifetime-prolonging Dual Battery System Scheduling for Drone Flights

14 In this section, the scheduling results comparison among the utilized algorithms and the
 15 validation of the new battery lifetime are presented. The characteristic dual system scheduling time
 16 sequence results are displayed in Fig. 6.

17 It can be seen from the figure that the online probabilistic scheduling algorithm gives a rather
 18 frequent switch between the new and SLB sets. Conversely, the online deterministic scheduling
 19 algorithm gives a stable battery usage state, since it considers the accumulated cost since the last

Figure 6: Battery operation scheduling result comparison

1 switch time and is, therefore, less sensitive to the fluctuation in drone power level. DP results are
 2 the benchmark as it owns the information in the whole timespan, whereas online algorithms have
 3 the information in the current time step and historical data.

4 In Fig. 6(b) where the drone power level is comparatively more stable than the rest, DP also
 5 gives limited switch times. In the others where drone power experiences a sudden increase or drop,
 6 DP results also tend to switch between the new and SLB to seek the optimal answer. From the
 7 switch sequence results, the online deterministic scheduling algorithm more resembles the solution
 8 quality of DP.

9 Based on the switch sequence results derived from different algorithms, the validation is
 10 performed to assess the consistency of the amortized operation cost and the effectiveness of
 11 extending the new battery lifespan with the dual battery power supply system. With the operating

1 sequence and power of two batteries, the Simulink model runs iteratively to simulate battery
 2 charge/discharge processes. When the battery reaches the end-of-life state with degraded capacity,
 3 it is replaced with the corresponding battery type, either new or second-life. And after all delivery
 4 flight time duration is finished, the average lifetime of all eliminated new batteries is computed and
 5 the number of both new battery and SLB replacements is counted.

6 There are in total 41800 drone delivery flights, each in around 20 minutes. As the drone energy
 7 consumption is fixed given the flight route in each delivery task, both the dual battery power supply
 8 system and the drone with a single new battery pack spend the same amount of electricity. Thus the
 9 cost of electricity charging is the same and can be neglected in the comparison.

10 The numerical results are summarized in Table 2. For comparison, drone operation with only
 11 one new battery pack is also tested and denoted as the “original” case.

Table 2: Comparison of optimization results of different algorithms under two kinds of Li-ion dual battery system

	Optimization result objective (\$)		Average lifetime of new battery (hr)		Number of new battery replacement		Number of second-life battery replacement		Switch times	
	Bat 1	Bat 2	Bat 1	Bat 2	Bat 1	Bat 2	Bat 1	Bat 2	Bat 1	Bat 2
Original	-	-	59.54	77.42	240	184	-	-	-	-
DP	2057.17	2123.66	1081.41	221.92	13	64	258	138	1166	2403
Deterministic	2085.83	2148.61	695.93	183.37	20	78	251	125	204	200
Probabilistic	2132.07	2172.24	116.37	155.03	123	92	136	109	38121	37407

12 As can be seen from the table, the optimization result objective values record the total cost
 13 calculated by the algorithms in terms of operation cost and amortized maintenance cost during the
 14 whole flight. For Bat 1 and Bat 2, DP gives the optimal solution, as the entire power consumption
 15 is known in advance. And the objective values of the online deterministic scheduling algorithm
 16 satisfy the comparative ratio consistent with the proof in section 4.3.

17 In the switch times of the result sequence, the frequency of the switch is consistent with the
 18 situation shown in Fig. 6. In which the online probabilistic scheduling algorithm switches between
 19 the new battery and SLB most often. And the online deterministic scheduling algorithm is less
 20 sensitive to power oscillation.

1 In the examined number of battery replacement and the average lifetime of the new battery,
2 in the dual battery system, the service life of new batteries are extended more than in the original
3 case, with fewer replacements of the new battery bank. The new battery life is prolonged at the cost
4 of SLB, yet the overall drone operation cost is reduced with the priority given to minimizing the
5 expenses of drone services. And for Bat 1 since it has a smaller capacity (4.5Ah) compared to Bat 2
6 (5.7Ah), the number of totally required batteries is smaller for Bat 2.

7 Therefore, the economic efficiency together with the battery lifetime extension effects is revealed
8 by the verification. The proposed dual battery system configuration provides the drone with longer
9 endurance and stronger serviceability.

10 **6. Conclusions**

11 The drone delivery industry is becoming practical with the achievements of in-city delivery
12 and truck-drone cooperative service model. Aside from operational difficulties, concerns exist and
13 request to be overcome regarding high expenditure on Li-ion batteries. High-level and intensely
14 fluctuated drone power load renders shortened battery lifespan. Therefore, instead of operation
15 solely by one battery pack, the dual-battery operation is proposed to leverage their complementary
16 advantages and compensate for the shortages, as the SLB set can help to handle large power output
17 to protect the new battery set.

18 The lifetime-prolonging dual battery operation scheduling problem for drone operation is duly
19 formulated in the offline mode, in which the drone power demand is known for the whole timespan.
20 And the dynamic programming scheduling algorithm is used to solve the offline problem based on
21 amortized operation cost. An online deterministic scheduling algorithm is developed to simulate
22 practical flying without future information, and the switch sequence between the new battery and
23 SLB packs is produced.

24 For the validation of the algorithm, the proof of comparative ratio for the online algorithm
25 solution compared to the optimal solution value is given. Numerical results compare the objective
26 value and the number of battery replacements. It is shown in the simulation that the dual battery
27 operation mechanism supports a longer average lifetime of new batteries and fewer re-investments
28 of new batteries, leading to increased economic efficiency.

1 On one hand, the advent of the dual-battery system to aid drone delivery requires less capital
2 investment for the new battery pack and makes full use of the SLB resources. Mutual comple-
3 mentarity within such a power supply system enables improved coping with comparatively lower
4 reliability of SLB, and time-varying environmental conditions, and supports the more sustainable
5 management of Li-ion resources.

6 The designed dual battery electricity supply system can release its full potential and gain
7 economic profits under proper online scheduling and allocation for drone applications. The
8 proposed online scheduling approach provides the reference for the schedule control program and
9 the applicability of the battery swapping circuit within the drone. Future extensions can deal with
10 the planning of drone flights to be capable of serving more customers.

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